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Skill Development and Employment Opportunities For Youth: A Roadmap From Developing To Developed India

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Abstract

India, a country with the youngest population in the world i.e. 54% of the total population is below age of 25 years and over 62% of population is in the working age of 15-59 years leading to become a skilled capital in the world. As per the report of NSSO, 2011-12 (68th round) only 2.2% of the population lying between the age group of 15-59 years have gone through formal vocational training and 8.6% have gone through non-formal vocational training hence, we must focus on scaling up skill training efforts to achieve employability and social economic growth. As envisioned by the hon'ble Prime Minister Shri Narendra Modi India is on the path of transformation from developing to developed country by 2047 for which we are required to divide the demographic of India into employable skills who are trained and ready to enter in the industry. Therefore, it is important to enrich skill development in the youth to make them more creative and employable. For promotion of skills and development of entrepreneurship attributes in youth, Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship was established in the year 2014. As per the thoughts of hon'ble Prime Minister of India, "Skilling, reskilling and upskilling focussing on the multidimensional approach to make our youth more competitive is the biggest need of the hour. These endeavours are aimed at making the youngsters flexible and adaptable in the current fast changing job market."

Keywords Economic Superpower, Amrit Kaal, National Skill Development Mission, industry-academia collaboration, Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Kendra.

Introduction

India, an economic superpower will contribute more than 25% of world workforce by 2025. To achieve this target we need to skill our youth. Skilling plays a vital role in the growth of individual personality and increment in employment opportunities. Skilling has proven to be the golden key for "Amrit Kaal" representing a new Bharat with technical advancement, inclusive welfare, transition, climate change through energy, galloping towards a multi-trillion dollars' economy. However, India is currently facing severe shortage of well-trained skilled workers. It has been found that only 4.69% of the workforce in India[1] has undergone formal skill training in comparison to other countries like 68% in United Kingdom, 75% in Germany, 52% in USA, 80% in Japan, 96% in South Korea. A major section of educated workforce has minimal or no jobs so first it is important to make the youth skillful and thereafter impart the qualitative and practical education for social and economic growth of the country.

To inculcate the necessary skills in secondary and higher secondary education students' government has integrated skill development and new education policy forming a national

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education policy 2020. This policy provides vocational training to the students from the very early stage and also provides hand-on-training.

National Skill Development Mission has been started by the ministry of skill development and entrepreneurship with the objective to provide training to minimum 300 million skilled people by 2022 to promote skill development across the country. Approximately 3415 training centres and 721 Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Kendras (PMKKs) have been registered under national skill development mission. Various schemes and initiatives taken by the government to upskill and reskill with aim of providing employment opportunities to youth. Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY) has been launched to upskill the opportunities to migrant workers and students. As per data till July 2021, approx. 70,823 migrant workers have been benefitted. This scheme also focus on online skill development training by pilot mode for 15 batches. Primarily for skill development in rural, urban and tribal community government of India has initiated PMKVY, Jan Shikshan Vikas Yojana, National Apprenticeship Scheme. Employment for tribal youth is the major concern of this scheme.

There are several other initiatives like Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Kendra, Rozgar Mela, Udaan, school and higher education initiatives, India international skill centres (IISCs) and Pre-Departure Orientation Training (PDOT) introduced by national skill development corporation for promotion of skill development and generation of employment opportunities. The government has given Rs 210 crores for multidisciplinary education research improvement in technical education in budget 2021-22 to improve technical skills of the youth of India. More, to enhance entrepreneurial skills in youth Pradhan Mantri Yuva Yojana has been launched by government.

Objective of study

In this research paper we will discuss skill India mission, employability, schemes and initiatives started by government of India to enhance skill development and employment opportunities for youth and will identify the challenges which are required to be fulfilled for the purpose of skills employment market by 2030, also in skilling and entrepreneurship landscape in India.

Review of Literature

Seema Yadav (2024) The study discussed the skills among youth and the opportunities and challenges in skill development across the globe in the twenty-first century. The research also mentioned different strategies to increase skill development for the future workforce.

Jitendra Kumar, Garima Hooda (2024) the research paper discussed the skill development program, challenges and employment opportunities. It mentions the role and advancement of India through skill development. The study discussed various skill development projects of government of India and their difficulties in employability. The research paper mentioned many obstacles like lack of skilled and trained workers, conservative thinking, low pay, lack of standardization and lack of emphasis on non-technical skills as the main root cause of skill gap in India.

Mayank Makkar, Kiran Lamba (2024) the research paper examines the Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY) which has been launched by government of India in 2015 to make India skilled capital in the world through skilling, reskilling and upskilling. The research shown the descriptive and exploratory case study of Haryana using primary and secondary data to find out the need between trained outcomes, industry demands, resource allocation and quality driven training enhancements.

Jayshree Mehta, Pranjal Bhatt, Vikas Raval (2024) The research paper has focused light upon Viksit Bharat 2047 mission which is contingent to skill development in India and highlighted 4 pillars of Viksit Bharat – Yuva (Youth), Mahila (Women), Garib (Poor), Kisan (Farmers). The research paper explore the critical landscape of skill development in India emphasizing its importance in driving economic growth and enhancing workforce liabilities.

Balwant Singh Mehta, Ishwar Chandra Awasthi (2025) The research paper discusses the opportunities and challenges for economic growth. The study mentioned the issues of low enrolment and poor quality of education exists particularly in higher education, technical and vocational training. The research paper focused upon high youth unemployment rates along with low pay offered by informal sector and limited social security.

Ajay Sharma Chinnadurai, Mahera Imam The research study India's persistent challenge in relation to unemployment among youth despite the country's demographic

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advantage of world's largest youth nation. The research also highlighted the government initiatives such as Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA) which guarantees 100 days of unskilled work to rural households and other self-employment program which aims to promote entrepreneurship and self-development.

Deeksha Chaurasia, Punnam Veeriah (2023) The research paper discussed the categories of skill development programs available to students and understand the perceptions and expectations of students who have enrolled in a skill development program and determine their level of satisfaction with such programs. The study aimed to investigate the relationship between skill development opportunities and student's employability that bridge the gap between academic learning and practical job requirements.

Main Text

Role of National Skill Development Corporation to enhance skills and generate employment opportunities for youth.

Government of India has launched several schemes to make our population skill and thereby providing them employment opportunities. Achievements of Major schemes in different phases can be analysed in following manner.

- 1. Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY)**
- The scheme has been launched in different phases and versions to upskill youth and generate employment opportunities.
- 3. Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana 1.0 (2015-16)-** This scheme has been implemented by ministry of skill development and entrepreneurship through National Skill Development Corporation, sector skill councils and training providers. It was designed to provide skilled base training to youth and make them employable for sustainable livelihood. Under this 19.86 lakhs candidate were trained and 14.51 lakhs got certification.[2]
- 4. Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana 2.0 (2016-2020)-** After successful implementation of PMKVY 1.0 version 2.0 was launched to impart skills to 1 crore youth of India with budget amounted Rs 12000 crores. The scheme provided fresh skill development training to school dropouts, college dropouts and unemployed youth through short courses 200-500 hours. As on 31-12-2022, 110 lakh candidates were trained across the country. Make In India, Digital India, Swachh Bharat were some programs which were launched under PMKVY2.0. Total 110 lakh candidates have been trained and 91.53 lakhs got certified.[3]
- 5. Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana 3.0 (2020-21)-** After successful implementation of PMKVY1.0 and 2.0 third phase of flagship scheme- PMKVY3.0 introduced in January,2021. The scheme was initiated to incorporate learnings from PMKVY 1.0 and 2.0 and to assess skill gap and demand at district level. As on 31-12-2022, 7.37 lakh candidates got training and 4.84 lakhs got certification across the country.[4] Overall conclusion is that under Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana 1.0, 2.0, 3.0 total 1.37crore candidates have been trained and 1.10 crore are certified in the country. As per details found on skill India portal till 31-12-2022 total 24.36 lakh candidates were placed under STT and special projects.
- 6. Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana 4.0-** Under the umbrella scheme of skill India programme PMKVY 4.0 implemented between F.Y. 2022-26 with the aim of making existing ecosystem more flexible, swift and geared to meet the current challenges. Inclusiveness of SC, ST, women and other marginalised communities to get skill-based training and employment under this programme. This scheme emphasized on re-skilling, upskilling under recognition of prior learning. The scheme focussed on new age skills like industry 4.0, web 3.0, AI/ML, climate change, green economy and energy transition.[5]

Achievements of Skill Development Programme-

Scheme	Component	STT	RPL	Special Projects	Total Trained	Total Certified	Total Reported Placed
PMKVY 1.0	CSCM	1804206	181810	0(No Special Project in PMKVY)	1986016	1451636	253296
PMKVY 2.0	CSCM	3811857	6141870	213844	10167571	8496472	1911182
	CSSM	826360	N/A	6787	833137	656881	230393
PMKVY 3.0	CSCM	294873	176491	108702	580066	379421	30951
	CSSM	64547	86214	6645	157406	104615	10218
GRAND TOTAL		8202677	6586385	335978	15125040	11957905	2436040

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Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Kendra (PMKK)

To continue skill India mission, Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship (MSDE) has started state of art, visible and aspirational model training centres in every district of India. These model training centres are known as "Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Kendra". Under this scheme, the private training partners who are selected as RPF can take loan upto amount Rs 70 lakhs at a subsidized interest rate. As on 31-12-2022, 818 PMKKs was required to cover 707 districts and out of that 721 PMKKs have been established.

PMKK Centres Summary

Categories	Achievement
No of Districts*	763*
No of districts having PMKK allocated till date	707
No of PMKK's allocated till date	818
No of PMKK's established as on 31.12.2022	721

Udaan

This scheme is a special initiative of NSDC for the youth of Jammu & Kashmir. Under this scheme the graduates and post graduates of J&K are exposed to best corporates of India. 750 crore was allocated to NSDC by ministry of home affairs to enrich skill development in youth. 44369 candidates joined this Udaan programme out of which 38798 completed this training and 24184 have been offered jobs. Corporates like TCS, Apollo Medskills, KPMG, Yes Bank, Tata Motors, Future learnings, IL&FS, Vision India etc have been part of Udaan Mega selection drives to provide training to the youth of J&K.

Jan Shikshan Sansthan (JSS)

Formerly known as Shramik Vidyapeet his working in India since 1967 through a network of NGOs and from year 2000 it has been renamed as JSS. The main aim of this scheme is to provide occupational skills and technical knowledge of non/neo literates and persons having rudimentary level of education upto 8th standard and other school dropouts beyond 8th standard to increase efficiency, productivity and livelihood opportunities. At present 248 Jan Shikshan Sansthan in 27 states and 2 UTs are working out of which 17 JSS are not functional.[6]

Rozgar Mela

It is a ½ day event where many employers and job seekers come together to apply and interview for jobs. The Rozgar Melas are conducted for the age of 18-35 years with academic qualification 8th/10th/12th/ITI/Diploma graduates etc. through print advertisement, SMS, social media and workshops at college and university level.[7] From 1st January,2019 to 31st December,2019 more than 700 Rozgar Melas have been conducted in 28 states/UTs by NSDC, PMKKs, PMKVY, fee-based model training partners etc. Approx 2.18 lakhs registrations have been done and 93000 candidates have been selected by private companies in Rozgar Melas.

National Apprenticeship Promotion Scheme (NAPS)

This is a scheme which provides apprenticeship training with partial stipend support under the apprentice act,1961 to provide on-the-job experiential training. The scheme encourages more number of apprentice participants to participate in micro small and medium enterprises (MSME) from underserved and north-east region.[8]

Vocational Training Programme for Women

This programme provides skill training to women to generate employment opportunities under ministry of skill development and entrepreneurship. The scheme was launched in 1977 to bring women into economic activities with the help of vocational training programmes, self-employment and wage employment in industry.[9]

Financial Assistance for Skill Training of Persons with Disabilities

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This scheme has been implemented by department of person with disabilities for the purpose of skill training to person with at least 40% disability by the way of grant-in-aid for organising training programs to training institutes.

School and Education Initiatives

National Education Policy 2020 enlightened vocational education and National Skill Development Corporation is facilitating its implementation. To enhance educational opportunities and individual employability government of India sponsored vocationalization of secondary and higher secondary education to reduce the gap between demand and supply of skilled manpower.

Higher education Initiatives

To boost employability among students passing general courses government of India started industry apprenticeship programme with education. This apprenticeship programme includes general education (academic), skill component (classroom/lab) and on the job training (apprenticeship).

Skill India Mission

As per Prime Minister of India, Narendra Modi "To make this century of India, it is very important that the youth of India should be equally proficient in education as well as skill. When it comes to skills, the mantra should be "Skilling, Reskilling and Upskilling". To fulfil the demands of industry 4.0 government has realised the requirement of skill development till 2030 with objective to address the issue is skill India mission. As per government data of ASSOCHAM study in 2017, only 10% of the fresh graduates of India possess employable skills. Remaining 90% do not have skills to enter in corporate world.

Skill India Mission fulfils the insufficiency amongst the youth for skill development and employment opportunities. Skill India Mission will help in creating a platform which will help the youth to acquire skill as per the need. Skill India Mission helps in developing financial skills in a sustainable manner. One of the important aspect of skill India mission is "Rural India Skill" which focusses in maintaining soft and interpersonal skills for every job position till 2030. Most importantly under skill India mission, workforce gets the updated training as per international standards so that they can be prepare for industry 4.0.

Skill India Mission has special attention towards construction, banking, tourism, textiles, transportation etc. as these are highly demanding in country but scarce in skills. Hence, government of India decided to diversify the training programs as per the requirement of different and industries.

Achievement of Skill Development Corporation for Skill India Mission under Ministry of Skill Development Entrepreneurship-

1. Increment in number of ITIs from 10119 (2014) to 14740 (2022) i.e. achievement of 45.67%.
2. More than 4 lakhs seats were added since 2014 in the existing 24+lakhs seat i.e. achievement in seating capacity by 52%.
3. Seating capacity of trainers have been increased by 13.3%.
4. 414 it is under Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana 3.0 have been affiliated for short term courses.
5. 33 National skill training institute (19 exclusively for women) and 3 extension centres are working now.
6. Bharat Skills (<https://bharatskills.gov.in>) a digital repository to provide e learning videos, question bank, mock test etc has been launched by DGT.
7. 10848 centres have been opened to provide skill training under National skill development corporation and more than 9100 added since 2014 reflecting a growth of 524%.
8. 991 new enterprises started and 1071 already established enterprises scaled up through Pradhan Mantri Yuva Yojna.
9. To make youth aware about entrepreneurship and let the know about the entrepreneurial journey of other beneficiaries by You Tube channel "PM-Udyami Talks".
10. To promote entrepreneurship among migrants, tribal women, SC, ST, OBC, Transgenders, Rag Pickers training programme have been initiated to promote livelihood opportunities.

Challenges in Skilling and Entrepreneurship landscape in India –

Skill development in India faces a number of challenges, despite the country's growing demand for skilled workers across various sectors. These challenges includes mismatch between education and industry needs, a gap between the skills imparted by educational institutions and the actual skills demanded by employers, limited access to quality vocational training, insufficient infrastructure of well-established training centers, lack of industry-academia collaboration, societal biasness for traditional academic degrees, high Cost of training and development programs, especially in technical fields, automation and AI, geographical disparities, rural-urban division, lack of strong mentorship and guidance, limited career counselling couple with following points poses a major challenges in Indian skilling landscape .

1. Non-inclusion of entrepreneurship in formal education system.
2. Inadequate attention towards innovation-based entrepreneurship.
3. Insufficient wage premium for skilled youth.
4. Less women workforce participation in skill development and entrepreneurship opportunities.
5. Issue of mobility between skill and higher education programmes and vocational education.
6. Minimal participation of apprenticeship programmes for youth welfare.

Conclusion

Skill development is important for social and economic growth of a country. Skills and knowledge both are essential attributes to make youth skilful and employable. India, a youth-oriented country is leading to become a super economic power by 2047 as per vision of our Prime Minister, Shri Narendra Modi. The focus towards skill, reskill and upskill for youth has proven to be life changing tool in the journey of transformation building of nation. Schemes and initiatives launched by the government of India provided lot of opportunities to make individuals capable, self-dependent and skilful. Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana provided training to 1.37 crores candidates out of which 1.10 crore got certification and 24.36 lakhs candidates got placement under STT and special projects which itself is a big success in the journey of a developing nation. Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana 4.0 provide opportunities to marginalised communities and women to get skill based training to become independent. 721 Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Kendras have established till date. Companies like Tata Motors, TCS, Yes bank, Apollo, Vision India etc have provided training to 38798 youth of Jammu & Kashmir out of which 24184 have offered jobs. 248 Jan Shikshan Sansthan in 27 states and 2 UTs are working to provide occupational skills and technical knowledge. Rozgar Melas have been conducted to provide employment opportunities to 93000 candidates. Initiative like vocational training programme for women started to enhance women workforce participation in economic activities of the country. Financial assistance to person with disabilities provided to give them skill-based training. Overall conclusion is that government of India is making visionary efforts to transform India from developing to developed country by allocating proper budget, providing required resources to the training centres to give the youth skill development training for better employment opportunities. Although, there has been significant progress in skill development initiatives in India, addressing the challenges requires a multi-pronged approach. This includes aligning educational curricula with industry needs, improving access to vocational training, enhancing the quality of instructors, reducing the stigma surrounding vocational education, and focusing on lifelong learning for workers. Policymakers, educational institutions, and industry leaders must work together to create a more robust, inclusive, and effective skill development ecosystem in India.

PMKVY has been a game-changer in terms of improving employability and providing skill training at scale. By emphasizing inclusivity, industry partnerships, and both technical and soft skill training, the program has empowered millions of young Indians to secure better livelihoods, build sustainable careers, and contribute to make Indian economy as a developed economy. However, the program still faces challenges like quality assurance, geographic disparities, and a need for further integration with the rapidly evolving job market, but its achievements in building a skilled workforce are undeniable.

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